

Science-Matrix

Genomics in Norway

May 2003

Overview of Research in Genomics in Norway

Prepared for
Genome Canada

Science-Metrix

Genomics in Norway

Overview of Research in Genomics in Norway

May 2003

Prepared for
Genome Canada

Science-Metrix specializes in the measurement and evaluation of science, technology and innovation. Our data collection and assessment methods include bibliometrics, scientometrics, technometrics, surveys and interviews, environmental scans, monitoring and intelligence gathering. We perform program and policy evaluations, benchmarking and sector analyses, market studies and strategic planning.

514.495.6505 ▪ 4572 avenue de Lorimier ▪ Montréal ▪ Québec ▪ Canada ▪ H2H 2B5
info@science-metrix.com ▪ www.science-metrix.com

Executive Summary

This report presents an overview of genome research in Norway using data from the Internet and from the Medline database.

Part I presents an overview of genomic research programs in Norway. In Norway, genome research is financed by a single government agency that provides financial support via a national research programme on functional genomics (FUGE). This program supports the research activities organized through ten technology platforms. Although Norway's global output in genomics papers is fairly low overall – the country lags behinds the other Scandinavian countries - Norwegian genomics has grown steadily during the last decade. Part I also presents data from the Internet on Norwegian universities, government and health sector institutions as well as companies that are active in the field.

Drawing from the Medline database, Part II examines the distribution of papers in genomics by sector, institution, city, and researcher. The distribution of research in genomics in Norway is concentrated in three locations:

Oslo: its output of papers is unmatched: it hosts the leading university and four of the nine leading hospitals. Almost all of the country's leading researchers come from the leading hospital, located in Oslo.

Bergen: it ranks second in scientific output, hosts the second most productive university and second most productive hospital.

Tromsø: the city ranks third in terms of scientific output and hosts the third most productive university.

The private sector represents a very low proportion of Norway's scientific output (1% of scientific papers).

The views presented in this report are those of Science-Metrix and do not necessarily reflect the opinions of Genome Canada.

I. An Overview of Genomics in Norway

In 1814, Norwegians resisted the cession of their country to Sweden and adopted a new constitution. Sweden then invaded Norway, but agreed to let Norway keep its constitution in return for accepting the union under a Swedish king. Rising nationalism throughout the 19th century led to a 1905 referendum granting Norway independence. Although Norway remained neutral in World War I and proclaimed its neutrality at the outset of World War II, it was not able to avoid a five-year occupation by Nazi Germany (1940-1945). Neutrality was abandoned in 1949 when Norway became a member of NATO. Discovery of oil and gas in adjacent waters in the late 1960s boosted Norway's economic fortunes. Oslo opted to stay out of the EU in a November 1994 referendum.

Norway is a prosperous nation with no external debt, combining free-market activity and targeted government intervention. Although it has recently moved ahead with privatization, the government still controls key areas of the economy through large-scale state enterprises. The main economic activities are high-tech fishing and aquaculture, shipbuilding, forestry and petroleum exploitation. Norway being highly dependent on its oil production and international oil prices (in 1999, oil and gas accounted for 35% of exports), Norwegians worry about the next few decades when oil and gas will begin to run out, as they currently rank at the top worldwide in terms of quality of life (CIA. 2002. *The World Factbook 2002*).

The local currency is the Norwegian Krone (1 Krone = CAN \$0.20). Norway's population and labour force are 15% that of Canada's. In Norway, the GDP per capita is 8% higher (US \$31,800) than in Canada (\$29,400, see Table 1).

Table 1. Basic Socio-Economic Statistics

	Norway	Canada
Area (sq km)	324,220	9,976,140
Population (July 2002 est.)	4,525,116	31,902,268
Labour force (2001 est.)	2,400,000 (53% of pop.)	16,400,000 (51%)
GDP*	US \$143 billion	US \$923 billion
GDP per capita*	US \$31,800	US \$29,400
Government type	Constitutional monarchy	Parliamentary democracy

* Purchasing power parity – 2002 est.

Source: CIA. 2002. *The World Factbook 2002*.

Between 1990 and 2001, Norway published 4,483 papers indexed by Medline (measured by first author of paper and Norwegian affiliation). This compares to 38,250 papers published by Canada during the same period (see Figure 1). The output in genomics in Norway grew slightly more rapidly (7.6% year-on-year average) than in Canada during the 1990s (6.7%).

Norway's scientific output in genomics is surpassed by that of other Scandinavian countries such as Denmark and Sweden (Table 2). This gap coincides with statistical data that show that Sweden and other Scandinavian countries surpass Norway in terms of R&D investments: Norway invests only 1.65% of its GDP in to R&D compared to 3.78% in Sweden, 3.22% in Finland and 2.09% in Denmark (GERD as a % of GDP – OECD Main Science and Technology Indicators, 1999).

This underinvestment and, the particularly low investment into basic life science research, recently formed the object of strong complaints on the part of researchers involved in the development of a national programme on functional genomics and centres of excellences in the field of molecular life sciences and biotechnology (*Nature*, 2002, Scandinavian Supplement 420, 13-15). Recognized as a world leader in applied research on marine resources, petroleum exploitation and shipbuilding, the Norwegian government's policy is to focus on applied rather than basic research. Nevertheless, researchers are optimistic and foresee positive developments with the creation of a new programme in proteomics (FUGE) by the Research Council of Norway and the forthcoming creation of new centres of excellence in the life sciences.

Table 2. Total number and average number of papers published in genomics by Norway and some other Nordic countries, 1990-2000

	Countries		
	Norway	Denmark	Sweden
Annual average number of papers	361	687	1,587
Total number of papers	3,967	7,554	17,457
Papers per million inhabitants	69	157	180

Source: Compiled by Science-Metrix using the Medline database.

National Research Programs in Genomics

Extensive research on the Internet reveals that genomic research is mainly funded by one major central government agency through a national research initiative called FUGE – functional genomics in Norway.

Founded in 1993 through the merger of five separate Norwegian research councils, the *Norges forskningsråd* (Research Council of Norway) is a key player in genome research funding. Its medicine and health division supports long-term basic research in biochemistry, molecular biology, cellular biology and physiology, while other government programmes support applied research-oriented projects in, for example, the field of bioproduction and processing. Independent researcher-initiated science projects in target areas such as biotechnology are covered by the science and technology program. Traditionally, this governance structure addressed the financing of biotechnology and genetics, but did not target genomics. From 2002, the Research Council of Norway started to manage a specific fund for research activities in functional genomics.

In January 2001, the Norwegian government received a research plan drawn-up by a national committee formed of many Norwegian research institutions who foresaw the need to substantially increase Norwegian allocations to research in functional genomics. For its first year in operation, this "bottom-up" initiative received 100 million Norwegian kroner from the Fund for Research and Innovation (2002 National Budget), and the project administration was mandated to the Research Council of Norway. FUGE mainly focuses on providing technology platforms as a service to the entire Norwegian research community. The platforms are driven by well-organized, active research groups that received funding for their research activities (see Table 3).

Table 3. List of the 10 technology platforms supported by the FUGE national program

Technology Platforms	Research Institutions Involved
Norwegian Arabidopsis Research Center (NARC)	UiO, NTNU and the Agricultural University of Norway http://boneslab.chembio.ntnu.no/NARC/NARC.html
The Norwegian Bioinformatics Platform (CBU)	Computational Biology Unit at UiB http://bccs.unifob.no/cbu/
The Norwegian Centre for Integrative Genetics (CIGENE)	Agricultural University of Norway, University of Oslo, AKVAFORSK, MATFROSK' NTNU http://www.cigene.no
The Norwegian Network of Human Research Biobanks and Health Studies (BIOBANKS FOR HEALTH)	Norwegian Institute of Public Health http://www.fhi.no/tema/biobank/
The Norwegian Centre for Microarray Technology (NMC)	NTNU, UiB, UiO - DNR http://www.mikromatrise.no
The Norwegian Structure Biology Centre (NORSTRUCT)	University of Tromsø www.chem.uit.no/NORSTRUCT/
The Norwegian Molecular Imaging Centre	University of Oslo
The Norwegian Molecular Imaging Centre	University of Oslo
The Norwegian Transgenic Animal Facility	University of Oslo

Source: <http://www.forskningsradet.no/fag/andre/fuge/teknologiplattform/index.html>

The research groups within the FUGE technological platforms collaborate closely with the Swedish functional genomics consortium SWEGENE (www.swegene.org). This Swedish network includes the Chalmers University of Technology, Göteborg University, Lund University and the Lund Institute of Technology. The exchange of microarray and proteomic technologies is now well underway between the two networks (*ELSO gazette: e-magazine of the European Life Scientist Organization*, Issue 12, December 2002).

A new cross-border biotech cluster, the so called "MedCoast Scandinavia," is emerging from the Oslo and Göteborg regions in Sweden. One of MedCoast's aims is to create links between the major Norwegian public research fund, FUGE, and the Swedish fund, SWEGENE, as well as between universities, research networks and regional industries. FUGE's plans to invest 150 million kroner in 2003 and the 100 million Swedish kroner investment to be made over a five-year period by Swegene (funded by the Wallenberg Foundation) offer a more promising horizon for biomedicine and bioscience in Norway.

With the intention of bringing more Norwegian researchers and research groups to a high international standard, the Research Council of Norway recently initiated a Centres of Excellence (CoE) scheme. From the thirteen centres selected recently for the Norwegian CoE scheme, only one biomedical research institute was selected, creating widespread disappointment in the biomedical community. The *Centre for Molecular Biology and Neuroscience* (CMBN) comprises eleven research groups from the University of Oslo, and the Rikshospitalet is the sole Norwegian CoE in the field of biomedical research. The CMBN investigates the role of DNA repair and genome maintenance mechanisms in preventing neurological disease and brain aging and focuses on the development and application of stem cell technology for the treatment of neurological disease. Of the 155 million kroner funding for all the centres of excellence, the CMBN receives 21 million kroner per year. The NRC has plans to nominate another five or six centres by 2006, and the research community is optimistic because an initial proposal to establish a molecular life science institute is currently being considered (*ELSO gazette: e-magazine of the European Life Scientist Organization*, Issue 12, December 2002).

The Salmon Genome Project (www.salmongenome.no) is a major international genomics research program in Norway supported by the Research Council of Norway. Its goal is to enhance the knowledge of the salmon genome through generation and analysis of genomic data. The project is operated under collaborative efforts between seven Norwegian research groups. The project focuses on genome organization and gene function through the development of genetic and physical maps and gene sequencing. Data interpretation using bioinformatics is an important part of the project, which is supported by the Biotechnology Centre of Oslo. In collaboration with Canadian partners, 55,000 expressed sequences have been generated (*Genome Biology*, Volume 3, Number 7, 2002:1-4). The total cost of this initiative is estimated to be 350 million kroner (Norwegian Computing Center).

Genome Research in Norwegian Universities

Whereas Part II of the report measures scientific output using scientometric methods, this first part presents a summary of the data made available by organizations on the Internet. These universities are listed in Annex IA. The main player in the field appears to be the *Universitetet i Oslo* (University of Oslo - UiO). The UiO has an inter-faculty steering board called EMBIO (<http://www.embio.uio.no/english/>), appointed to stimulate and coordinate research in molecular biology, biotechnology and bioinformatics. EMBIO's activity is closely linked with the national program for research in functional genomics (FUGE). In terms of research, the Biotechnology Centre of Oslo (BiO) which is located in the Oslo Research Park is home to five research groups with interest in genomics and employs researchers from three UiO faculties : Natural Sciences, Medicine and Dentistry. The centre focuses on the use of technology derived from molecular biology and molecular genetics and operates a core facility that provides services to the scientific community consisting of 1) protein sequencing, 2) peptide synthesis, 3) DNA sequencing and 4) oligonucleotide synthesis. Many other UiO departments, such as the Department of Biochemistry and the Biological Institute¹ as well as the Institute of Medical Microbiology², part of the National Hospital, are active in genomics and genetics. The Department of Molecular Biology focuses on molecular mechanisms for DNA repair, microbial genome maintenance and bioinformatics, while Clinome Bioinformatics³ is part of the FUGE Bioinformatics platform, although this platform is mainly driven by the Computational Biology Unit at the University of Bergen.

The Norwegian EMBnet node (www.no.embnet.org), located at the Biotechnology Centre of Oslo (BIO at UiO), also offers a focal point for bioinformatics in Norway. EMBnet Norway provides a variety of services and tools such as software, access to major biological databases and training programmes in bioinformatics. Training in bioinformatics is also available at the University of Bergen, and a Bioinformatics forum in Bergen (BiB) was established in 1999 for the bioinformatics users and developers community in Bergen.

The University of Bergen (UiB) is very active in genomic and proteomic research. UiB's proteomic unit was in fact selected to develop the proteomic technology platform of the FUGE program. On the other hand, the Sars International Centre for Marine Molecular Biology works on the basic biological processes in marine organisms, using functional and comparative molecular methods on marine models, and has done work on the zebrafish, salmon genome, marine vertebrates and

¹ See <http://www.matnat.uio.no/bkj/english.html>; and <http://biologi.uio.no/index.html>.

² Home of the program for sequence database searches based on sequence similarities (SALSA - DNA and Protein Sequence Database Search); <http://dna.uio.no/salsa/about.html>

³ <http://www.cbo.uio.no/index.html>

immune system of fish. UiB's Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology and Department of Anatomy and Cell Biology are both involved in gene cloning, sequencing and clustering.

The University of Tromsø's (UiT) Department of Molecular Biotechnology (<http://www.fm.uit.no/info/imb/amb/>) is home to three research groups with interests in genomics. The UiT is also home to the *Norwegian Structural Biology Centre (NorStruct)*, the FUGE technological platform on structural biology. The Norwegian College of Fishery Science's Department of Marine Biotechnology (www.nfh.uit.no) at the UiT performs genomic research on the marine biotechnology of salmon and different marine organisms.

The Department of Chemistry and Biotechnology's Laboratory of Microbial Gene Technology at the Agricultural University of Norway (<http://www.nlh.no/ikb/IKB-Home.html>) work mainly on the molecular developmental biology of plants, plant genomic analysis and on population and evolutionary genetics.

The Norwegian University of Science and Technology's (NTNU) Medical Biotechnology department focuses on DNA repair and gene expression. The aim of NTNU's research is to describe human genomic classifiers based on gene expression patterns. NTNU has an on-line depository of genomic and proteomic data (<http://boneslab.chembio.ntnu.no/databases.html>). A NTNU's spin-off company, Interagon, plans to develop products and services for the discovery of patterns in the huge volumes of data found in the biotechnology sector.

The Norwegian School of Veterinary Science's Department of Biochemistry, Physiology and Nutrition works on post-genomic research using transgenic fish models.

Also noteworthy is a Norwegian consortium called the Norwegian Microarray Consortium⁴, which is composed of the Technical University of Trondheim, the University of Bergen and the Norwegian Radium Hospital (DNR at the University of Oslo). This consortium is supported by the Norwegian Research Council, the Norwegian Cancer Society and private donations received by hospitals.

Genome Research in the Health Sector

The most important player in genome research in the health sector is a collective known as the University Hospitals of Oslo, its most important constituent being the Norwegian Radium Hospital (DNR) (www.dnr.org). The Institute for Cancer Research is one of the DNR's main components doing R&D in genomics. More particularly, the Department of Genetics focuses on genetic and epigenetic changes in cancer development and studies the patient's constitutional

⁴ The Norwegian Microarray Consortium - <http://www.med.uio.no/dnr/microarray/english.html>

genotypes, tumour genotypes and phenotypes related to risk and treatment response. Other departments of the institute are also active in genomics (Cell Biology, Biochemistry, Immunology, Biophysics and Tumor Biology). The DNR is currently establishing a DNA microarray resource unit for the parallel analysis of the activity of thousands of genes (<http://www.med.uio.no/dnr/microarray/english.html>).

Another major university hospital in Oslo is the Rikshospitalet (The National Hospital), which performs research in genomic aspects of oncology. The Trondheim University Hospital's (St. Olavs Hospital) research activities in genomics and bioinformatics are closely linked with those of the NTNU and the SINTEF, while the University Hospital of Tromsø's Department of Medical Genetics works in close collaboration with the UiT's Institute of Medical Biology (IMB).

The Haukeland University Hospital in Bergen is the largest hospital in Norway and is, as one may expect, affiliated to the University of Bergen. The hospital is a significant player in genome research, more specifically in the area of the genomic mapping of the Nordic family and the treatment of the regional Sjögren's syndrome. The three most active units are the Gade Institute, the Center for Molecular Medicine and the Department of Medical Genetics.

The National Institute of Public Health's (*Nasjonalt folkehelseinstitutt*) Department of Population Health Sciences performs research on the Norwegian Biobanks for Health, a base cohort established for genetic epidemiological research (www.fhi.no/tema/biobank/). The institute is a merger of the National Institute of Public Health, the National Health Survey, Bergen's Medicinal Birth Registry and the Department of Drug Consumption Statistics of the Norwegian Medicinal Depot. The new institute is the home of Biobank's FUGE human genomic databank platform.

Finally, the *Den Norske Kreftforening* (Norwegian Cancer Society), a national voluntary organization, performs work in genomics within its cancer research program in collaboration with universities (www.kreft.no). The active institutions in the health sector are listed in Annex IB.

Genome Research in Governmental and Non-Governmental Organizations and Institutes

SINTEF is the largest independent research organization in Scandinavia. Its contract research for industry and the public sector (www.sintef.no) generates more than 90% of its income (1.7 billion), with only 7 % coming in the form of basic grants from the Research Council of Norway. The Department of Chemistry's biotechnology section performs research in genomics, proteomics and bioinformatics. SINTEF and the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) closely collaborate by sharing research facilities and driving common projects.

MATFORSK, the Norwegian Food Research Institute, is another independent, non-profit research organisation managed by the Agricultural Food Research Foundation (www.matforsk.no). The

institute carries out projects related to cloning genomic DNA segment methods and to genomic approaches in food applications.

Norsk Regnesentral (Norwegian Computing Center) is a private, independent, non-profit foundation that has an expertise in statistical R&D specifically related to bioinformatics.

The National Veterinary Institute is the Ministry of Agriculture's scientific institution for veterinary research, diagnostic, analytic and other support services (www.vetinst.no). The institute runs a program called *Qpcrgmofood* on genetically modified organism detection with DNA array-based PCR techniques. The active institutions in the sector are listed in Annex IC.

Genome Research in the Private Sector

No pan-Norwegian organization appears to promote or finance genomic research in the private sector. However, in 2001, the Norwegian Bioindustry Association (www.biotekforum.no) started to promote the growth of Norwegian biotechnological trade at the national, European and world level. The association represents more than 50 high-tech biotechnology companies. Most of the country's biotechnology companies are located in the greater Oslo area.

The *Oslo Technopol* is a focal point for research in biotechnology and biomedicine (www.oslo.technopole.no) that hosts many biotech companies and closely interacts with universities and colleges. There are also close to 100 biotech companies that are located within the Oslo Innovation Centre (www.forskningsparken.no). Similarly, the *Ås BioScience Park* located in Ås aims to transform research-based results and knowledge-based projects into profitable business activities (www.bioparken.no).

There are around 10 firms that publicize their research or their products in genomics on the Internet (Annex II). Most of these are small start-ups, and some of them are spin-offs of university research centres. There are also a few multinational corporations with headquarters or important branches in Norway (e.g. Merck, Nycomed).

* * *

Compared to other Scandinavian countries, the scientific output of Norwegian institutions in genomics is relatively low. Nevertheless, genomics, proteomics and bioinformatics have strong roots in the academic sector. In fact, the government only recently started supporting "bottom-up" academic initiatives with the goal of reinforcing the country's strengths in functional genomics. Cancer genomic research and bioinformatics are well-developed in Norway's academic sector. Genome research in aquaculture is one of the most promising avenues of collaboration between Canada and Norway, and, in fact, there is already some collaboration within the Salmon genome project.

II. Leadership Structure of Genomics in Norway

This part examines the distribution of papers in genomics by sector, institution, city and researcher. The Medline database is used since more than 91% of papers in genomics are published in journals classified in the fields of Biomedical Research and Clinical Medicine. From 1990 to 2001, Norway published around 4,500 genomics papers that were indexed by Medline (measured by first author of paper and Norwegian affiliation).

Distribution of Papers by Sector

In Norway, 52% of papers in genomics are written by researchers affiliated with universities (Figure 2). Authors from the health sector also play an important role in the development of research in genomics, since 42% of papers are authored by researchers affiliated with a health centre, a medical clinic or a hospital (including university hospitals). With 1% of the scientific output, private firms play a similarly marginal role as in Sweden where private firms account for about 2% of the scientific output. Governmental organizations author 1% of papers which is extremely low compared to other European countries.

As Figure 3 clearly shows, the production of papers amongst university-level institutions in Norway is fairly concentrated. In particular, with more than 850 papers, the University of Oslo is responsible for 41% of the output, and the University of Bergen for 21% with 443 papers. The University of Tromsø is third with less than 270 papers; the *Norges veterinærhøgskole* (Norwegian School of Veterinary Science) located in Oslo, published about 190 papers, while the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) located in Trondheim published about 170 papers in genomics indexed by Medline. The *Norges landbrukshøgskole* (Agricultural University of Norway) located in Ås, which is part of the greater Oslo area, published about 130 papers. These six universities account for 46% of the Norwegian output in genomics.

Figure 4 lists the most active institutions in the health and hospital sector. Not surprisingly, three quarters of them are university hospitals, and two thirds are located in Oslo (*Rikshospitalet*; *Radiumhospitalet*; *Ullevål universitetssykehus*; *Aker universitetssykehus*). In fact, Oslo hospitals account for more than 70% of the Norwegian output in the health sector. The two leading Norwegian hospitals in genome research are the Rikshospitalet and the Norwegian Radium Hospital (*Radiumhospitalet*), both affiliated to the University of Oslo, making this university the country's central institution in terms of scientific output in genomics.

Two governmental institutes have a place in the ranking of the most active institutions in the health sector: the Norwegian Institute of Public Health (186 papers) and the National Institute of Occupational Health (43 papers).

Figure 5 lists the most active institutions in the governmental and independent research sector. The Norwegian food research institute (MATFORSK) is the leading independent non-profit institute, with 82 papers published in the last 12 years. SINTEF-UNIMED, the largest independent research organization in Scandinavia, ranks second with 30 papers. The National Veterinary Institute, the Ministry of Agriculture's official scientific institution for veterinary research, ranks third with 29 papers published during this period. The sector represented by government and independent institutions has the same importance as the private sector in terms of scientific output in Norway.

Like in Sweden, publications by private firms in Norway constitute a small proportion (1%) of the papers published in the field of genomics. Data presented in Table 4 reveal that 26% of the output in this sector stems from the pharmaceutical multinational Nycomed Pharma A/S, which is located in Oslo. The private medical microbiology laboratory A/S Telelab is one of the leading laboratories in microbial molecular genetic testing in Norway.

**Table 4 Ranking of Leading Enterprises in Genomics in Norway.
Number of Papers by City, 1990-1999**

Rank	Enterprise	Headquarters Location	Oslo	Skien	Tromso	Others, Unknown	Total
1	Nycomed Pharma A/S		18				18
2	A/S Telelab			14			14
3	Fiskeriforsknings				9		9
	Others (n=14)		15	1		12	28
Total			33	15	9	12	69

Source: Science-Metrix (Medline)

Position of Norwegian Cities in Genomic Science

Figure 6 shows that Oslo is Norway's capital of genomics, producing 60% of the country's output by city. This greater metropolitan area hosts several leading institutions active in the field of genomics, notably, the University of Oslo, and several multiple hospitals active in genomic research (*Rikshospitalet*; *Radiumhospitalet*; *Ullevål universitetssykehus*; *Aker universitetssykehus*). The city of Bergen ranks second, with 16% of Norway's scientific output, while Tromsø ranks third with 8%.

Leading Norwegian Researchers in Genomic Science

Figure 7 reveals that Oslo hosts all Norwegian leading researchers except one, Professor Ingolf F. Nes, who is located at the Agricultural University of Norway in Ås. This comes as no surprise, since Oslo clearly dominates the output in genomics amongst Norwegian cities. Moreover, all the leading researchers in Oslo come from institutions affiliated with the University of Oslo (UiO), the most productive university. The most productive researcher and the third most productive researcher are located at the *Radiumhospitalet*, whereas the second most productive researcher is located at the UiO's Institute of Immunology (IMMI). It is worth noting that even if the UiO's *Rikshospitalet* ranks first in terms of research hospital, most of the leading researchers (43%) come from the *Radiumhospitalet* rather than the UiO (29%) and the *Rikshospitalet* (19%). Only one other institution hosts a leading researcher, the *Ullevål universitetssykehus*. The relatively small place occupied by the other sectors (government, private and independent) is also confirmed by the absence of leading researchers in those sectors.

Figure 7 Papers in Genomics by Leading Researchers in Norway, 1990-2001

Source: Science-Metrix (Medline)

Annex IA

Norwegian Universities Performing Research in Genomics

University	Department
<i>Universitetet i Bergen</i> (University of Bergen)	Proteomics Unit at University of Bergen (PROBE) http://pcom3.ifff.uib.no/probe/intro.html
	Department of Biochemistry and Molecular Biology http://www.uib.no/med/avd/ibmb/index_e.shtml
	Department of Anatomy and Cell Biology http://www.uib.no/med/avd/iac/
	Sars International Centre for Marine Molecular Biology http://www.uib.no/fa/sars/
<i>Universitetet i Oslo</i> (University of Oslo)	Centre for Molecular Biology and Neuroscience (CMBN) http://www.sdu.dk/Nat/bmb/index.shtml
	Centre for Proteome Analysis in Life Sciences http://www.proteome-analysis.dk/
	Biotechnology Centre of Oslo http://www.biotek.uio.no/
	Computational Biology Unit (CBU) http://www.cbu.uib.no/
	Institute of Immunology (IMMI) http://immunologi.no/
	Department of Medical Biochemistry / Department Group of Basic Medical Sciences http://www.med.uio.no/imb/medbiokj/index.html
	Department of Biochemistry http://www.biokjemi.uio.no/english/
	Department of Physics, Biophysics Group http://www.fys.uio.no/biofysikk/english/
	Institute of Medical Microbiology http://dna.uio.no/mi/indexe.html
	EMBIO (Steering board) http://www.embio.uio.no/english/
	<i>To be implemented</i>
The Norwegian Centre for Microbial Technology	
The Norwegian Molecular Imaging Centre	
The Norwegian Transgenic Animal Facility	
<i>Universitetet i Tromsø</i> (University of Tromsø)	The Norwegian Structural Biology Centre (NORSTRUCT) http://www.chem.uit.no/NORSTRUCT/
	Faculty of Medicine http://www.adm.uit.no/infoavd/eprofil/medfak.htm
	Norwegian College of Fishery Science - Department of Marine Biotechnology http://www.nfh.uit.no/index.asp
	Institute of Medical Biology http://ws.uit.no/websim2/index.php?SiteId=23&PageId=401&EditState=

	1&RecordId=none
<i>Norges veterinærhøgskole</i> (Norwegian School of Veterinary Science)	Department of Biochemistry, Physiology and Nutrition http://www.veths.no/
<i>Norges teknisk-naturvitenskapelige universitet (NTNU)</i> (Norwegian University of Science and Technology)	The Faculty of Medicine http://www.medisin.ntnu.no/eng/ Department of Cancer Research and Molecular Medicine http://www.medisin.ntnu.no/ikm/eng/ Department of Medical Biotechnology http://www.ntnu.no/satsingsomraader/medisinsk_teknologi/contact.htm
<i>Norges landbrukskøskole</i> (Agricultural University of Norway)	Department of Animal Science http://www.nlh.no/ Department of Chemistry and Biotechnology - Laboratory of Microbial Gene Technology http://www.nlh.no/ikb/IKB_homeE.html
Inter-University Research Organization	CIGENE - Centre for Integrative Genetics http://www.nlh.no/?avd=40 Norwegian Arabidopsis Research Center (NARC) http://boneslab.chembio.ntnu.no/NARC/NARC.html The Norwegian Centre for Microarray Technology (NMC) http://www.mikromatrise.no

Annex IB

Norwegian University Hospitals and Health Institutions Performing Research in Genomics

Hospital	Department
<i>Rikshospitalet</i> (Rikshospitalet University Hospital)	LIIPAT - Laboratory for Immunohistochemistry and Immunopathology (Institute of Pathology) http://www.med.uio.no/ilab/inst/patologi/liipat/
<i>Radiumhospitalet</i> (Norwegian Radium Hospital)	Institute for Cancer Research http://www.dnr.org/default.cfm?pageID=48 Department of Cell Biology http://www.dnr.org/default.cfm?pageID=169 Department of Biochemistry http://www.med.uio.no/dnr/Inst/biochem/biochem.html Department of Genetics http://www.dnr.org/default.cfm?pageID=98&avdID=6 Department of Pathology http://www.dnr.org/default.cfm?pageID=448 Department of Immunology http://www.dnr.org/default.cfm?pageID=252&avdID=25 Department of Biophysics http://www.dnr.org/default.cfm?pageID=122&avdID=3 Department of Tumour Biology http://www.dnr.org/default.cfm?pageID=141&avdID=9

<i>Haukeland Sykehus</i> (Haukeland University Hospital)	Centre for Molecular Medicine http://www.helse-bergen.no/avd/medgen/forskning/cgh/cgh.htm
<i>Ullevål universitetssykehus</i> (Ullevaal University Hospital)	Gades Institute http://www.uib.no/med/avd/patolog/gades.html
<i>St. Olavs Hospital - Universitetssykehuset i Trondheim</i> (University Hospital in Trondheim)	Department of Medical Genetics http://www.ulleva.no/default.asp?file=english_summary.xml
<i>Regionsykehuset i Tromsø</i> (University Hospital in Tromsø)	The Faculty of Medicine http://www.medisin.ntnu.no/eng/
<i>Aker universitetssykehus</i> (Aker University Hospital)	Department of Animal Science http://www.nlh.no/
<i>Sentralsjukehuset i Rogaland (SiR)</i>	www.aker.uio.no/ http://www.sir.no/index_1024.asp

Governmental Health Institutions

<i>Folkehelseinstituttet</i> (Norwegian Institute of Public Health)	BIOBANKS for Health http://www.fhi.no/tema/biobank/
<i>Statens arbeidsmiljøinstitutt</i> (National Institute of Occupational Health)	http://www.stami.no/eng/index.htm

Annex IC

Norwegian Governmental and Non-Governmental Organizations Performing Research in Genomics

<i>MATFORSK</i> (Norwegian Food Research institute)	http://www.matforsk.no/web/hjem_e.nsf
<i>SINTEF-UNIMED</i>	http://www.sintef.no/units/unimed/index.html
<i>Veterinærinstituttet</i> (National Veterinary Institute)	http://www.vetinst.no/
<i>Forsvarets forskningsinstitutt</i> (Norwegian Defence Research Establishment)	http://www.mil.no/felles/ffi/start/English/
<i>AKVAFORSK Institutt for akvakulturforskning</i> (Institute of Aquaculture Research)	http://www.akvaforsk.no/
<i>Havforskningsinstituttet</i> (Institute of Marine Research)	www.imr.no/
<i>Norsk institutt for skogforskning</i> (Norwegian Forest Research Institute)	www.nisk.no/
<i>Norsk Regnesentral</i> (Norwegian Computing Center)	http://www.nr.no/documents/samba/
<i>PLANTEFORSK Norsk institutt for planteforskning</i> (Norwegian Crop Research Institute)	www.planteforsk.no

Annex II Companies Active in the Fields of Genomics, Proteomics and Bioinformatics in Norway

This list comprises enterprises that were active in genomics between 1990 and 2001 or that acquired firms that were active in genomics during those years.

Affitech A/S

Oslo Research Park
Gautstadalléen 21
0349 Oslo Norway
Tel: +47 22 95 87 58
Fax: +47 22 95 83 58
Email: info@affitech.com
Internet: www.affitech.com

Biomolex A/S

P.O. Box 180 Vindern
0319 Oslo Norway
Tel: +47 22 14 70 87
Fax: +47 22 14 70 88
Email: info@biomolex.no
Internet: www.biomolex.com

Dynal Biotech

P.O.Box 114 Smestad
0309 Oslo Norway
Tel: + 47 22 06 10 00
Fax: + 47 22 50 70 15
Email: dynal@dynalbiotech.com
Internet: www.dynal.no

Interagon AS

Olav Kyrres gt. 3
7489 Trondheim Norway
Tel: +47 922 77 000
Fax: +47 455 94 458
Email: info@interagon.com
Internet: www.interagon.com

MedProbe A/S

P.O. Box 2640 St.Hanshaugen
0131 Oslo Norway
Tel: + 47 23 32 73 80
Fax: + 47 23 32 73 90
Email: medprobe@medprobe.com
Internet: www.medprobe.com

MSD (Norge) A/S (Merk)

Solbakken 1
3011 Drammen Norway
Tel: +47 32 20 73 00
Fax: +47 32 20 73 10
Email: msdnorge@msd.no
Internet: www.msd.no

PubGene A/S

Forskningsveien 2A
P.O. Box 180 Vinderen
0319 Oslo Norway
Tel: +47 92 88 58 83
Fax: +47 22 13 79 11
Email: mail@pubgene.com
Internet: <http://www.pubgene.com/>

Norferm D/A

P.O. Box 8005
4068 Stavanger Norway
Tel: +47 51 63 59 00
Fax : +47 51 63 59 01
Email: norfermfirmamail@norferm.com
Internet: www.norferm.no

Nycomed Pharma A/S

Drammensveien 852
P.O. Box 205
1372 Asker Norway
Tel: +47 66 76 30 30
Fax: +47 66 76 30 40
Internet: www.nycomed.no

SalmoBreed A/S

Bontelabo 2
5003 Bergen Norway
Tel: +47 97 65 09 10
Fax : +55 33 37 99
Email: post@salmobreed.no
Internet: www.salmobreed.no

Telelab A/S

Strømdaljordet 4
P.O. Box 1868 Gulset
3703 Skien Norway
Tel: +47 35 50 57 00
Fax: + 47 35 50 57 01
Email: miljolab@telelab.no
Internet: www.telelab.no